

STREAMLINED COMPOSITE MODELING WORKFLOWS WITH MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMISATION

G. Goldbeck¹, J. Seyfarth², B. Bidaine², D. Di Stefano^{3*}

¹ Goldbeck Consulting Limited, Cambridge, United Kingdom, ² e-Xstream engineering, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, ³ ESTECO spa, Trieste, Italy

* Corresponding author (distefano@esteco.com)

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1 Introduction

Multi-disciplinary and multi-objective optimization (MDO) techniques have had significant impact on engineering design processes in the last decade. They enable the user to make informed design decisions that take different aspects of the problem and often conflicting objectives into account in an integrated fashion. Modern MDO software supports the integration of different models and conditions and provides the user with efficient workflows and decision support based on trade-off analysis.

Micromechanical modeling of composites with mean-field or explicit methods involves a series of steps including the fitting of appropriate material models to experimental data, homogenization and calculation of response curves for different conditions and material compositions.

The current paper demonstrates how an integration of micromechanical composite modeling with MDO software helps to streamline the workflow and enable more efficient design decisions. As an example we present the case of a polymer composite with glass fiber and glass bead fillers.

2 Multi-component composite optimisation

Consider the design of a polymer-glass fiber composite where some of the fibers are to be replaced by glass beads. This would lower the total cost, improve some properties such as thermal anisotropy and processing, but lead to a decrease in mechanical properties.

The task includes running and analyzing separate simulations for different compositions, i.e. a series of micromechanical simulation steps which we have integrated into a single workflow. In particular, the micromechanical simulation is driven by the mean-

field homogenization method in the Digimat software from e-Xstream, which we have integrated in the MDO platform modeFRONTIER from Esteco.

The modeFRONTIER workflow, shown in Fig. 1, explores the composition design space using a Design of Experiment (DOE) approach with a Genetic Algorithm method (NSGA-II). The objective function consists of stiffness and anisotropy.

As a result, we obtain an immediate overview of properties for the whole range of bead/fiber fractions explored. For example, Fig. 2 shows the non-linear response behaviour as a function of filler composition, with strain applied in the direction transverse to the fibers. The run indicated by the arrow, replacing 50% of fibers by beads, shows only a 3% loss in the stress levels that can be sustained. In addition, the workflow enables a trade-off analysis between the loss of strength and the reduced thermal anisotropy.

3 Reverse engineering (RE) of material models

Based on micromechanical models it is possible to fully integrate processing simulations in the computation of the performance of composite parts. The quality of results of such a coupled analysis strongly depends on the quality of the material model used. Best procedures are to reverse engineer the material model to anisotropic measurements on the composite material. Depending on the targeted performance, a large number of experimental results have to be taken into account. For anisotropy, it is common to measure at least 2-3 different orientations. For temperature and strain rate dependencies, three variations each can be seen as a minimum. Combining all these strongly increases the number of curves targeted in the final model.

Basically, the fitting procedure amounts to a multi-parameter, multi-objective optimization problem. We have therefore utilized the sophisticated optimization methods available in modeFRONTIER to fit Digimat model response curve to experimental data. Typically, one unique set of parameters needs to reproduce test data from all different conditions, such as different temperatures and/or strain rates. We will present results from a complex test case involving monotonic tests at different temperatures and strain rates as well as creep tests at different temperatures and stresses.

4 Conclusions

The integration of Digimat with modeFRONTIER provides a range of opportunities for streamlining workflows for the design of composites. The scenarios that will be discussed include parametric studies of multi-component composites and reverse engineering of material models. The modeFRONTIER workflow captures the whole design space within one simulation and the analysis enables the user to consider the trade-off between different target properties.

In future, the integration of in-depth study of representative volume elements as it is available also in the Digimat software would allow for a microstructure based optimization of composites with a wide range of potentially complex target functions regarding the material properties. In addition, with the MDO approach an enhancement to the processing and local microstructure workflow becomes possible where the solver of the processing software is triggered to produce these results on-the-fly. The optimization dimensions are henceforth broadened by taking into account directly the processing step for the composite part.

Fig. 1. Digimat integrated into a multi-objective optimization workflow in the modeFRONTIER software. Input-output flow is from top to bottom, and the design evaluations flow from left to right.

Fig. 2. Thermo-mechanical analysis in transverse direction for a range of compositions. The arrow indicates the case of equal amounts of fibers and beads, with just a small loss of strength.